

1 Article

2 **Research of MEMS pressure sensor stability with PDA-NFL circuit**3 **Mikhail Basov**4 Dukhov Automatics Research Institute (VNIIA), Moscow 127055, Russian Federation;
5 engineerbasovm@gmail.com

Abstract: The stability of pressure sensor chip output characteristics using the piezoresistive method in the form of microelectromechanical system (MEMS) is one of the most important features for sensors, which simultaneously demonstrates the relevance of the principles for design construction and the choice of fabrication technology for all element structures. The research analyzes the changes in the useful signal, as well as errors in mechanical and temperature characteristics of highly sensitive pressure sensor chips, which are more explicitly dependent on external factors. The main feature of this development is the application of a new electrical circuit in the form of piezoresistive differential amplifier with negative feedback loop (PDA-NFL) utilizing bipolar junction transistors (BJT), which allows to achieve a balance between high sensitivity, small chip area and low errors. This research considers the variations of two batch with pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL samples (area 4.00x4.00 mm²) for range of 1 kPa after 4.5 years (8 samples, sensitivity $S_{1\text{ after}} = (40.6 \pm 6.4)$ mV/V/kPa, nonlinearity $2K_{NL\ 1\text{ after}} = (0.81 \pm 0.15)$ %/FS) and range of 5 kPa after 3.0 years (14 samples, sensitivity $S_{5\text{ after}} = (11.2 \pm 1.8)$ mV/V/kPa, nonlinearity $2K_{NL\ 5\text{ after}} = (0.10 \pm 0.06)$ %/FS). The study demonstrates the unidirectional influence of residual mechanical stresses (RMS) from the pressure sensor assembly design on sensitivity and nonlinearity when pressure is applied from different sides of chip, initial membrane deflection, and temperature hysteresis errors.

Keywords: pressure sensor, stability, electric circuit, transistor, sensitivity, nonlinearity, temperature characteristics

25 **1. Introduction**

26 Pressure sensors in the form of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) based on
27 piezoresistive and capacitive effects are the two most popular types of compact sensors for
28 mass production in specific industry sectors. Currently, the market of MEMS pressure
29 sensors can be divided into 5 sectors: automotive (tire pressure management system
30 (TPMS), pressure sensors for engine and fuel tank, airbag and exhaust gas monitoring),
31 medical (invasive blood pressure monitoring, respirators, inhalers, and ventilators), vari-
32 ous types of industrial industry (pressure sensors in nuclear power plants, robotics in
33 manufacturing; heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems), consumer
34 electronics (smartphones and smart watches, Internet of Things, drones, and smart home)
35 and aerospace (Full Authority Digital Electric Control (FADEC), hydraulics, airflow and
36 altitude data) [1]. The MEMS pressure sensors market size is estimated to be USD 2.36 bil-
37 lion in 2023 [2]. By 2028, the market size is projected to reach USD 3.19 billion with a
38 compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of about 6.2%. The competition in the sales market
39 for both MEMS and any microelectronic devices depends either on the ability to mass
40 produce elements with low cost and acceptable quality depending on the application, or to
41 create something unique and find its special field, as, for example, Yokogawa Electric
42 Corporation has done with resonant method pressure sensor chip, which have a record of
43 output signal stability for 15 years [3]. Looking at piezoresistive and capacitive pressure
44 sensors, it can be noted that companies such as Bosch Sensortec, Amphenol NovaSensor,
45 STMicroelectronics, TE Connectivity, Honeywell, Murata, and other manufacturing lead-

Citation: To be added by editorial staff during production.

Academic Editor: Firstname Last-name

Received: date

Revised: date

Accepted: date

Published: date

Copyright: © 2024 by the author. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

ers not only produce more than millions or tens of millions of elements per year, but also combine the ability to develop exclusive high-tech ideas that are phased into new series of sensors with improved performance.

Any implementation of a MEMS development requires years to confirm the regularities of its characteristics with dozens of repetitions to fabricate a batch of wafers or micro-assembly construction. The time to implement a new design or series of operations in the manufacturing process for an element depends on the significance and innovation of the proposal itself. A significant factor for a development is not only the repeatability of the characteristics from batch to batch, but also the stability of all its parameters over time within the same batch. Often the stability of parameters is only considered in terms of the change in zero output signal and sensitivity. It is also a relevant area of research to analyze not only the useful signal, but also the variation of errors in mechanical and temperature characteristics on time. Stability and temperature hysteresis of output signal are uncompensated errors that largely determine the quality of the sensor itself [4-7]. For example, the nonlinearity and temperature coefficient of output signal can be minimized by hardware processing using an application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) [8-10], but the correlation coefficients can be changed over time. As a result, this factor leads to an error increasing of pressure sensor as a whole. Especially, this analysis is relevant for highly sensitive pressure sensor chips. Therefore, the proposed study will aim to investigate in detail the behavior of one of the promising designs for low pressure ranges with stability analyzing of all parameters after several years. Two types of mechanical structure of sensor chip for differential pressure measurement up to 1 kPa and 5 kPa ranges will be considered. The development of pressure sensor chips for low ranges is one of the most interesting tasks, as its solution simultaneously raises the issues of maintaining the balance between high sensitivity, low errors, overall dimensions and the possibility of stable mass fabrication [11-17]. The high response to capacitance changes when exposed to vibration is one of the main reasons why the capacitive method was not considered as a working method at the initial stage of this development. Also, despite the advantages of low power consumption, ease of fabrication and small chip size of capacitive pressure sensors, it has a very high nonlinearity error and require the mandatory use of an external processing circuit or ASIC to convert the capacitance into an electrical signal [18-23].

There are two main factors for piezoresistive pressure sensor chips that affect the useful signal and errors. The first factor is related to leakage currents of pressure sensor chip due to the limiting ability of closing the p-n junction for high and low-alloyed regions of piezoresistors (PRs) on wafers with single-crystal structure [24-27], defectivity [28] and embedded charge in the surface silicon oxide [29], and due to the effect of the difference in the temperature coefficient of expansion (TCE) between aluminum (or other metal) and silicon on the thin membrane structure [30-32]. The second factor is the relaxation of residual mechanical stresses (RMS) in the micro-assembly structure of pressure sensor chip [33-37]. In many important article reviews [38-41] about the achievements of various MEMS pressure sensor developments present theoretical and experimental data only for small number of samples (1-3 elements) or often without specifying the number. Also, the developers analyzed the output characteristics only at a certain moment immediately after fabrication (excluding thermo- and barocycling) without real running time and without specifying the scatter of values among samples in a batch.

The main distinctive feature of considered development is the application of a new electrical circuit in the form of piezoresistive differential amplifier with negative feedback loop (PDA-NFL) using two non-deformable bipolar junction transistors (BJTs) and eight PRs for pressure sensor chip instead of the classical Wheatstone bridge with four PRs, the application of which is known already from 1950s [42]. In the course of previous studies, it was experimentally proved that several advantages of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL are achieved with respect to analogs with Wheatstone bridge circuit:

1. The samples of development for range of 60 kPa demonstrated the sensitivity growth in 3.5 times ($S = 1.9 \text{ mV/V/kPa}$) while maintaining the overall chip dimensions ($4.0 \times 4.0 \text{ mm}^2$), the design and geometry of membrane and low errors; as well as the possibility of reducing the overall chip dimensions in 2.4 times while maintaining the same sensitivity values. [43-47];
2. The comparative analysis was carried out in relation to a series of analogs [49-55] for similar range of 5 kPa in the article [48]. If we compare the output characteristics taking into account the achievement of the highest values of sensitivity for analogs, the most relevant development is the pressure sensor chip with CBMP membrane [49]. The pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL and analog with CBMP membrane has the same nonlinearity errors ($2K_{NL} = 0.27\%/FS$), while pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL has membrane area by 65% smaller, sensitivity in 2.2 times higher ($S = 11.2 \text{ mV/V/kPa}$), mechanical hysteresis and repeatability in more than 8 and 6 times lower, respectively;
3. The analysis of the characteristics for pressure sensor chip was also carried out for the development with PDA-NFL circuit for range of 1 kPa [56] relative to the most relevant analogs for ultra-low pressure range up to 0.5 kPa [57,58]. All parameters of the development and analogs were considered under the same conditions and in the pressure range up to 0.5 kPa. The analog [57] has the highest known sensitivity for classical piezoresistive pressure sensor chips. The sensitivity of this analog reaches the values of 65.0 mV/V/kPa , which is 44% higher than on the development with PDA-NFL circuit ($S = 44.9 \text{ mV/V/kPa}$). On the other hand, the advantages of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL achieved by 30% lower nonlinearity error ($2K_{NL} = 0.26\%/FS$), used by 35% smaller membrane area, and be able to withstand overload pressures in 5 times higher than the analog. The other most relevant analog with BMQI membrane [58] has the sensitivity in 2.5 times lower and membrane area in 3.1 times larger than the development with PDA-NFL circuit. But at the same time the nonlinearity error of the analog with BMQI membrane is only $2K_{NL} = 0.14\%/FS$, which is 1.9 times lower.

Each development has a set of its own advantages and disadvantages, the ratio of which makes it possible to use a pressure sensor chip for different type of industry. It is worth noting that most of the current research about pressure sensor chips for low range actually lacks information on the analysis of temperature characteristics and long-term stability over a long period of time. In this study, such analysis with certain additions will be provided to show how the parameters of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa after 4.5 years (8 samples) and of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa after 3 years (14 samples) change.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Working principle of the PDA-NFL electrical circuit

Only the basic features with some new additions on the design and fabrication of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL will be presented in Section 2, because the main focus of this research is precisely on analyzing the stability behavior of all output characteristics. The details of analytical and software modeling for the working principles of PDA-NFL electrical circuit (Fig. 1a) were demonstrated in previous researches [43-48,56], taking into account the technological features of fabrication and the formation of topologies for the construction of pressure sensor chip structures. Also, variations of using deformable and non-deformable BJT with horizontal structure of p-n-p type conductivity and vertical structure of n-p-n type conductivity were researched by using the theory of piezjunction effect for BJTs [42,59-62]. Each type of BJT has a certain set of values for all eight PRs, which is necessary to achieve a balance between high sensitivity, low error for the temperature coefficient of output signal and low output noise. As a result of theoretical and

experimental comparative analysis it was proposed to use two non-deformable BJTs with vertical structure of n-p-n type conductivity, which is located on chip frame, and eight PRs of p-type conductivity, which is located in pairs on four areas of maximum mechanical stress (MS). The four areas of maximum MS is created on the thinned part of membrane between three concentrators of MS in the form of rigid islands (RIs) and edges of the chip frame (Fig. 1b,c). The change of PRs resistance under the pressure occurs mirror symmetrically with different signs for the two opposite branches of PDA-NFL circuit.

Figure 1: Pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL: (a) Electrical circuit; (b) Photo of the front or top side with labeling of element arrangement; (c) Schematic representation of the membrane structure from the back side and its geometrical parameters [56].

For example, when pressure is applied from the membrane, when the output signal values increase, there is resistance decrease of PRs R_{b11} , R_{em1} , R_{c2} and R_{b22} , because it is located in the areas of tension between RIs (closer to the middle of pressure sensor chip), and resistance increase of PRs R_{b21} , R_{em2} , R_{c1} and R_{b12} , because it is located in the areas of compression between RIs and the chip frame (closer to the perimeter line of the thinned part of membrane). Table 1 shows all necessary electrical parameters for correct operation of PDA-NFL circuit without specifying technological differences.

Table 1. Parameters of PDA-NFL electrical circuit [56].

Electrical parameters		Values
Supply voltage U_{sup} , V		5,0
Base current I_b , μ A		4,6
Gain β		145
BjT	Base-emitter voltage ($U_b - U_{em}$), V	0,8
	Collector-base voltage ($U_c - U_b$), V	0,8
	Collector potential U_c , V	2,8
PR	$R_{b11, b21}$, kOhm	4,47
	$R_{b12, b22}$, kOhm	2,98
	$R_{c1, c2}$, kOhm	3,33
	$R_{em1, em2}$, kOhm	1,79

The advantage of PDA-NFL circuit relative to the classical Wheatstone circuit is not only in the possibility of combining more PRs due to the presence of three BjT contacts in the opposite branches, but due to the correct balance of potential and current shifts in PDA-NFL circuit at all other equal conditions on supply voltage and influence of pressure. Finally, this balance allows us to change the potential difference on the collectors of two opposite BJTs more significantly, which makes role of output signal for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL. The working principle of PDA-NFL circuit is fundamentally different from

176 the principle of amplifying the output signal by using a signal processing circuit on the
177 same area of pressure sensor chip or as separated chip of ASIC in a single assembly [63-66].
178 The goal of PDA-NFL circuit application is proving the possibility of obtaining high sensi-
179 tivity (or, as a consequence, reducing the chip area and increasing the number of samples
180 on the wafer) while maintaining low errors for all output characteristics, including tem-
181 perature characteristics, where, for example, the uncompensated error of temperature
182 hysteresis does not increase in proportion to the increase in sensitivity.

183 2.2 Technological peculiarities of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL fabrication

184 The pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL is created on 3-inch diameter silicon wafers with
185 an epitaxial structure, where the epitaxial layer is n-type conductivity silicon with the
186 crystallographic plane (100), resistivity $\rho_{ep} = 1.5 \text{ Ohm}\cdot\text{cm}$ ($N_{Cep} = 3 \cdot 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and thickness
187 $x_{ep} = 11 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$; and the substrate is p-type conductivity silicon with the crystallographic
188 plane (100), resistivity $\rho_{sub} = 10 \text{ Ohm}\cdot\text{cm}$ ($N_{Csub} = 8 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and thickness $x_{sub} = 390 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$.
189 Epitaxial structure of silicon wafers is required to form pockets where the BJTs are lo-
190 cated. The BJTs are isolated from each other and other elements of chip PDA-NFL by
191 creating separated regions of p⁺-type conductivity up to the substrate layer. A contact
192 pad is created on the front or top side of chip PDA-NFL to deliver the lowest ground
193 potential to the substrate. It helps to close the p-n junction between the epitaxial layer and
194 the substrate with separation regions. The BJTs are located on the non-deformable frame
195 of chip PDA-NFL and connected to the main body of PRs due to aluminum metallization
196 layers with thickness $W_{al} = 0.8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and high-alloyed conductor regions of p⁺-type con-
197 ductivity ($N_{sp+} = 7.4 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $x_{jp+} = 3.6 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $R_{sp+} = 17 \text{ Ohm}/\text{cm}^2$). The main body of PRs is
198 located in the crystallographic direction $\langle 110 \rangle$ and created by low-alloyed regions of
199 p-type conductivity ($N_{sp-} = 8.0 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $x_{jp-} = 1.8 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $R_{sp-} = 200 \text{ Ohm}/\text{cm}^2$) with a high
200 piezoresistive coefficient $\pi_{44p-} = 1.26 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1}$ (at room temperature) [67]. The high-alloyed
201 regions of p⁺-type conductivity with low piezoresistive coefficient $\pi_{44p+} = 0.32 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1}$ is
202 also created along the crystallographic direction $\langle 110 \rangle$. The high-alloyed regions of
203 p⁺-type conductivity is required to connect the low-alloyed regions of p-type conductiv-
204 ity and metallization on the area of the thinned part of membrane. The high-alloyed re-
205 gions of p⁺-type conductivity ranges from 3.7% to 10.6% of the total resistance rating for
206 various PRs. Metal tracks and contact pads are created only on chip frame with width of
207 $20 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and at least $80 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ from the edge of the thinned part of membrane. Two
208 low-alloyed regions of p-type conductivity for different PRs with topological pattern
209 width of $10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ by lithography and a gap between PRs of $16 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ were located in the areas
210 of maximum MS between RIs or RI and the chip frame. The size of the gap between PRs
211 is designed in such a pattern to eliminate the overlap of space charge regions between
212 two diffusion regions at a certain potential, taking into account the component from lat-
213 eral diffusion of impurity, silicon oxide etching wedge and possible error by lithography.
214 A detailed description of technological route with the sequence of operations and diffu-
215 sion modes was presented in publications [43-48,56].

216 The thinned part of membrane and chip PDA-NFL itself have square shapes for the
217 top view (Fig. 1c). The mechanical part of chip PDA-NFL is created only on the back side
218 by liquid anisotropic etching in the solution of 30% KOH at $T = 85^\circ\text{C}$ with small addition
219 ($6 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$) of isotropic etching in the solution of $\text{HF}:\text{HNO}_3:\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$ (2:9:4) to increase the
220 mechanical strength of membrane structure. A deposited layer Si_3N_4 (PECVD) [68,69]
221 and ProTEK polymer coating [70,71] utilizes as a protection during the liquid etching of
222 silicon. The geometrical dimensions of mechanical part for chip PDA-NFL are presented
223 in Table 2 for two pressure ranges of 1 kPa and 5 kPa. The scatter of the thickened part of
224 membrane as the main parameter for mechanical structure is rather high (about $\pm 21\%$ of
225 the nominal) for two types of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL. The scatter of the thickened
226 part of membrane is naturally the reason for the high scatter of sensitivity and errors. It is
227 reasonable to apply deep reactive ion etching (DRIE) or liquid stop-etching [72-76] for
228 further realizations of highly sensitive pressure sensor chips.

Table 2. Membrane geometrical parameters for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL [48,56].

Geometrical parameters	Values	
	1	5
Pressure range P, kPa	1	5
Chip side length L, μm	4000 \pm 50	
Chip thickness H, μm	400 \pm 5	
Thickness of the thickened part of membrane W, μm	9 \pm 2	10 \pm 2
Length of membrane side A, μm	2810 \pm 15	2260 \pm 15
Gap width between RI and frame D, μm	39 \pm 5	23 \pm 4
Length of RIs rib Z, μm	270 \pm 50	790 \pm 60

The last fabricated batch of chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa is used the form of thin supmembrane silicon oxide (SO) with thickness $W_{\text{SiO}_2} = 55$ nm over the surface of the thinned part of membrane. The samples of chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa have a step structure of silicon oxide on the thickened part of membrane with thickness from 0.18 to 0.42 μm depending on the doping areas. It was experimentally proved for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa in the study [48] that the formation of SO allows to reduce not only the difference in sensitivity and nonlinearity when differential pressure is applied from different sides of chip, but also to significantly reduce the errors of temperature characteristics.

After finishing of the whole technological route, the chips PDA-NFL on the wafer are selected according to the leakage current between the doped areas of all electrical circuit structure and substrate. The leakage current at p-n junctions at room temperature does not exceed $I_{\text{leak}} < 50$ nA at reverse bias $U_{\text{res}} = 40$ V, which partially guarantees the achievement of low errors of long-term stability from the side of chip PDA-NFL operation. The charge in silicon oxide from Na^+ , Cl^- and other ions was measured during the fabrication of chip PDA-NFL after each diffusion process with oxidation. The charge did not exceed $Q < 5 \cdot 10^{10}$ C/cm². Additionally, it is worth noting that further fabrication of chip PDA-NFL also needs to take into account the complex component from the variation of BJT parameters on time as for single element [77-79]. Thus, this part of Section shows how the first factor problems from Introduction about minimizing the error of long-term stability were solved.

2.3 Technological peculiarities of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL assembly

The geometry of assembly structure for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL has a significant influence on the errors, because the RMS relaxation from all kinds of chip-to-body bonding has effect by time and temperature changing (the second factor about long-term stability from the Introduction). It is possible to consider different types of chip PDA-NFL micro-assembly and other MEMS in general before the moment of connection with metal, ceramic, plastic or other materials cases [80,81]: hydrophilic or hydrophobic direct bonding of silicon [82], anodic bonding [83], coupling through glass (frit) [84,85], eutectic [86,87], adhesive bonding [88,89], reactive compound [90,91], thermal compression [92,93] or laser-assisted coupling [94]. There are also rather exotic micro-assembly technologies, such as in the design of the PS³ [95]. The variety of bonding types and materials used is quite extensive, where each has its own advantages and disadvantages depending on applicability. For these reasons, the C65-1 silicon-to-silicon via glass (frit) bonding process was chosen as the method for micro-assembly construction, because this process had been already proven in company fabrication. In addition to the bonding type for the micro-assembly, the design of intermediate elements up to the sensor cases [3,4,95] as well as the type and application of adhesive for the micro-assembly-to-body connection [33,35,36] plays a significant role in the reduction of RMS. This micro-assembly design uses a silicon intermediate element with area equal to the area of chip PDA-NFL and thickness of 400 μm , as well as a silicon pedestal in the form of regular parallelepiped with dimensions of 3.0x3.0x2.5 mm³ and a hole with diameter of 0.9 mm for pressure supply from the back side (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Assembly design for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL: (a) schematic representation; (b) photo of sample [48].

Pressure from the top side of chip PDA-NFL is applied through the hole in the lid of pressure sensor cases. The connection of micro-assembly of chip PDA-NFL with the case is made with an adhesive (glue). After all assembly operations and checks (including measurement of tightness with helium flow rate not more than $1 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{Pa/s}$), batches of pressure sensors chip PDA-NFL are tested for initial running-in of elements. The batches of assemblies are subjected to thermocycling (5 cycles from $T = -70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $T = +130 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during 24 hours) and barocycling (7000 cycles of five times overpressure depending on the range with 3-second hold at $T = +90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) to remove RMS.

3. Results and Discussion

The article [56] about the batch of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa and article [48] about the batch of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa presented mechanical and temperature characteristics, which were obtained in May 2019 for 14 samples and September 2020 for 22 samples, respectively. In September 2023, the batch of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa has 8 samples and the batch of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa has 14 samples, because some samples were used for subsequent customer studies. No additional artificial influences by electrical supply, pressure, temperature and other factors were made during 4.5 years for the batch with the range of 1 kPa and during 3.0 years for the batch with the range of 5 kPa. Thus, the research presents data on stability of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL after long storage in normal climatic conditions. The measurements of all samples were calculated as the arithmetic mean of 10 measurements during 5 seconds due to the increased noise component of output signal. The studies for two batches before and after long storage were conducted using identical equipment and under identical conditions including the upward position of the top side of chip PDA-NFL. The parameters of all analysed output characteristics by batches will be presented as "arithmetic mean \pm standard deviation" from the absolute values of each sample. The sign of parameter variation for each sample of the batch will be considered only for the long-term stability of output signal and the initial deflection of the membrane.

3.1 Mechanical characteristics

The next parameters are considered as mechanical characteristics at fixed temperature $T = +25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$: zero output signal, sensitivity or change of output signal when the nominal pressure is applied from the back or the top side of chip PDA-NFL, nonlinearity when the pressure is applied from the back or the top side of chip PDA-NFL (a measurement step is $\frac{1}{4}$ of the nominal range), as well as mechanical hysteresis and repeatability. Table 3 and 4 presents in detail the values of zero output signal and sensitivity for each sample of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for ranges of 1 kPa and 5 kPa, respectively, before (without

apostrophe) and after (with apostrophe) the long storage period, as well as errors of the long-term stability of zero output signal and change of output signal on nominal pressure.

Table 3: Values of zero output signal, sensitivity and errors of long-term stability for zero output signal and change of output signal on nominal pressure of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa before and after long-term storage during 4.5 years.

Samples/ Parameters	Before storage				After storage				Long-term stability	
	U_0 , mV	U_1 , mV	ΔU_1 , mV	S , mV/V/kPa	U'_0 , mV	U'_1 , mV	$\Delta U'_1$, mV	S' , mV/V/kPa	$dU_{0\text{ stab}}$, %/FS	$dU_{1\text{ stab}}$, %/FS
T1.11	-93,3	137,9	231,2	46,23	-88,0	132,4	220,4	44,09	2,3	4,6
T1.15	19,0	226,8	207,8	41,56	14,9	212,8	197,9	39,58	2,0	4,8
T1.26	-97,8	77,5	175,3	35,05	-95,1	79,1	174,2	34,84	1,6	0,6
T1.34	-21,6	161,6	183,3	36,66	-20,0	156,6	176,6	35,31	0,9	3,7
T1.48	22,4	267,5	245,1	49,01	21,8	273,8	252,0	50,39	0,2	-2,8
T1.64	10,1	178,2	168,2	33,64	10,1	171,4	161,3	32,25	0,0	4,1
T1.67	92,0	297,5	205,6	41,11	95,2	307,1	212,0	42,39	-1,6	-3,1
T1.68	-81,9	140,4	222,2	44,45	-78,5	152,4	230,9	46,18	1,5	-3,9
Module average	-	-	204,8	40,97	-	-	203,1	40,63	1,3	3,5
Modulus spread	-	-	27,5	5,51	-	-	31,3	6,26	0,8	1,3

Table 4: Values of zero output signal, sensitivity and errors of long-term stability for zero output signal and change of output signal on nominal pressure of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa before and after long-term storage during 3.0 years.

Samples/ Parameters	Before storage				After storage				Long-term stability	
	U_0 , mV	U_1 , mV	ΔU_1 , mV	S , mV/V/kPa	U'_0 , mV	U'_1 , mV	$\Delta U'_1$, mV	S' , mV/V/kPa	$dU_{0\text{ stab}}$, %/FS	$dU_{1\text{ stab}}$, %/FS
T5.5	-37,1	239,6	276,7	11,07	-39,5	229,6	269,2	10,77	-0,9	2,7
T5.11	18,3	258,5	240,2	9,61	13,8	250,3	236,5	9,46	1,9	1,5
T5.17	-26,2	275,2	301,4	12,05	-25,3	271,1	296,4	11,85	0,3	1,7
T5.18	-32,3	223,8	256,1	10,24	-31,7	219,6	251,3	10,05	0,2	1,9
T5.19	-26,2	283,5	309,7	12,39	-27,6	277,0	304,6	12,19	-0,4	1,6
T5.20	-37,5	205,0	242,5	9,70	-38,7	199,2	237,9	9,52	-0,5	1,9
T5.24	-27,3	289,4	316,8	12,67	-28,5	283,6	312,1	12,48	-0,4	1,5
T5.32	36,3	243,5	207,2	8,29	38,1	243,2	205,2	8,21	-0,9	1,0
T5.81	-12,7	322,9	335,6	13,43	-17,4	311,0	328,4	13,14	-1,4	2,2
T5.82	38,1	340,5	302,4	12,09	37,1	337,6	300,5	12,02	0,4	0,6
T5.86	-23,6	324,6	348,2	13,93	-31,7	307,7	339,4	13,58	-2,3	2,5
T5.90	34,0	290,1	256,1	10,24	32,8	284,2	251,5	10,06	0,5	1,8
T5.93	-37,0	329,5	366,5	14,66	-39,4	318,4	357,8	14,31	-0,7	2,4
T5.95	-13,9	230,9	244,9	9,79	-17,6	224,9	242,5	9,70	-1,5	0,9
Module average	-	-	286,0	11,44	-	-	280,9	11,24	0,9	1,7
Modulus spread	-	-	46,9	1,88	-	-	45,3	1,81	0,7	0,6

The calculation of parameters from Tables 3 and 4 was carried out using equations (1-4) under the condition that pressure was applied from the back side of chip PDA-NFL:

$$\Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5} = U_{1 \text{ or } 5} - U_0, \quad (1)$$

$$S = \Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5} / U_{sup} / \Delta P, \quad (2)$$

$$dU_{0 \text{ stab}} = (|U_0| - |U'_0|) \cdot 100\% / \Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5}, \quad (3)$$

$$dU_{1 \text{ or } 5 \text{ stab}} = (U_{1 \text{ or } 5} - U'_{1 \text{ or } 5}) \cdot 100\% / \Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5}, \quad (4)$$

where U_{sup} – supply voltage, which is equal to 5 V; ΔP – pressure difference between the back and the top side of chip PDA-NFL, which is equal to 1 kPa or 5 kPa; U_0 – zero output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 0$ kPa, mV; $U_{1 \text{ or } 5}$ – output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 1$ kPa or $\Delta P = 5$ kPa, mV; $\Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5}$ – change of output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 1$ kPa or $\Delta P = 5$ kPa, mV; S – sensitivity, mV/V/kPa; $dU_{0 \text{ stab}}$ – long-term stability error of zero output signal, %/FS; $dU_{1 \text{ or } 5 \text{ stab}}$ – long-term stability error of output signal change under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 1$ kPa or $\Delta P = 5$ kPa, %/FS.

The limit of zero output signal is less than 100 mV modulo for the batch of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa. The high unbalance of zero output signal is a consequence of using more PRs and two BJTs, but, as in the case of high noise component, this drawback can be eliminated by using ASIC. The sensitivity is equal to $S = (41.0 \pm 5.5)$ mV/V/kPa instead of the previously presented values of $S = (44.9 \pm 8.8)$ mV/V/kPa [56], because 6 of 14 samples with the best performance and slightly higher sensitivity were given to the consumer. If we look at the change of zero output signal modulus for each sample, it can be noted that in most cases the initial unbalance is reduced and the overall absolute batch error after 4.5 years is $dU_{0 \text{ stab}} = (1.3 \pm 0.8)$ %/FS. The change of sensitivity after 4.5 years occurred in a multidirectional shift with higher batch values of $dU_{1 \text{ stab}} = (3.5 \pm 1.3)$ %/FS.

The limit of zero output signal also remained the same as in [48] and didn't exceed 40 mV modulo for the batch of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa. 8 of 22 samples were also given to the consumer, so the sensitivity changed slightly and amounted to $S = (11.44 \pm 1.88)$ mV/V/kPa instead of $S = (11.24 \pm 1.81)$ mV/V/kPa. In contrast to the batch for range of 1 kPa, which may didn't have more samples for analysis, the samples of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa showed a multidirectional shift of zero output signal modulus and a unidirectional shift of sensitivity toward a values reduction. After analyzing the long-term stability results by batch, it can be noted that after 3.0 years the absolute error of zero output signal is $dU_{0 \text{ stab}} = (0.9 \pm 0.7)$ %/FS and sensitivity is $dU_{5 \text{ stab}} = (1.7 \pm 0.6)$ %/FS.

The study of nonlinearity is relevant to carry out on graphs in Fig. 3 with average values for batches, as it was done in research [48]. Calculation of nonlinearity error is carried out using the standard equation:

$$2K_{NL \ i} = \frac{\Delta U_i - \Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5} \cdot (\Delta P_i / \Delta P)}{\Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5}} \cdot 100\%, \quad (5)$$

where ΔP_i – pressure difference between the back and top side of chip PDA-NFL in $\frac{1}{4}$ steps of pressure ranges, i.e. 0.25/0.50/0.75/1.00 kPa for range of 1 kPa and 1.25/2.50/3.75/5.00 kPa for range of 5 kPa; ΔU_i – change of output signal under the influence of pressure ΔP_i , mV. Fig. 3 shows the dependences of nonlinearity error for two types of batches when pressure is applied from the back (blue line) and top (red line) sides of chip PDA-NFL. The pressure measurement step is $\frac{1}{4}$ of the range. The dotted line indicates the error before storage and the solid line indicates the error after storage. After fabrication of two batches for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL, there is a uniform trend in which the nonlinearity error when pressure is applied from the top side of chip is approximately 1.5 times higher than when pressure is applied from the back side of chip. It indicates the presence of unbalanced RMS from the sensor assembly design.

364 **Figure 3:** Graph for depending of nonlinearity error on pressure for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL
 365 for range of: (a) 5 kPa; (b) 1 kPa.

366 A perfect pattern of complete balance for nonlinearity error when pressure is ap-
 367 plied from the top side of chip is observed for range of 5 kPa after 3.0 years of storage
 368 (Fig. 3a). The overall batch error rates are $2K_{NL\ 5\ after} = (0.10 \pm 0.06) \%$ /FS, which is slightly
 369 lower than the lowest nonlinearity error rates before storage when applying pressure
 370 from the back side of chip PDA-NFL - $2K_{NL\ 5\ before, back} = (0.11 \pm 0.09) \%$ /FS.

371 The batch of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa after 4.5 years of
 372 storage also shows a significant reduction in nonlinearity errors by 38% to $2K_{NL\ 1\ after, back} =$
 373 $(0.81 \pm 0.19) \%$ /FS when pressure is applied from the back side of chip PDA-NFL and
 374 $2K_{NL\ 1\ after, top} = (1.24 \pm 0.54) \%$ /FS when pressure is applied from the top side of chip
 375 PDA-NFL. The balance of nonlinearity errors when pressure is applied from different
 376 sides is still not achieved (in contrast to the batch for range of 5 kPa), but the difference
 377 between the values has been significantly reduced.

378 It is possible to estimate the probable initial deflection of the membrane as addi-
 379 tional analysis on the effect of RMS for each sample by equation:

$$\Delta P_{def,1\ or\ 5} = \frac{U_0 - (U_{1\ or\ 5,back} + U_{1\ or\ 5,top})/2}{(U_{1\ or\ 5,back} - U_{1\ or\ 5,top})/2 \cdot \Delta P'} \quad (6)$$

380 where $U_{1\ or\ 5,back}$ – output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 1\ kPa$ or $\Delta P = 5\ kPa$
 381 from the back side of chip PDA-NFL, mV; $U_{1\ or\ 5,top}$ – output signal under the influence of
 382 pressure $\Delta P = 1\ kPa$ or $\Delta P = 5\ kPa$ from the top side of chip PDA-NFL, mV. It is worth
 383 noting that the thinned part of membrane has an initial deflection also due to the presence
 384 of RIs inertial mass. Tables 5 and 6 show the initial deflection of membrane for two batches
 385 before and after storage and the difference of its value module.

386 The values of the initial deflection of membrane for the two types of batches have
 387 different signs, which indicates the presence of both upward (positive value) and down-
 388 ward (negative value) deflection of the thinned part of membrane. The initial deflection has
 389 values from several Pa to several hundreds of Pa. The common feature of the RMS reduc-
 390 tion after long-term storage for two batches of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL is the
 391 changes of modulo values for the initial deflection with the same negative sign. This de-
 392 pendence shows that the mechanical structures of membrane try to reach a balanced state.
 393 Finally, 7 of 8 samples for range of 1 kPa have the downward deflection of membrane and
 394 13 of 14 samples for range of 5 kPa have the opposite upward deflection of membrane after
 395 long-term storage. This effect is probably due to the presence or absence of SO structure for
 396 pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL.
 397
 398

Table 5. Initial membrane deflection values for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa before and after long-term storage during 4.5 years.

Samples/Parameters	Deflection $\Delta P_{def, 1}$, Pa			
	No	Before storage	After storage	Change of modulo values
T1.11		-78,9	-49,3	-29,6
T1.15		-9,1	-0,9	-8,2
T1.26		-16,5	-5,4	-11,1
T1.34		-9,2	-7,3	-1,9
T1.48		-8,0	-7,8	-0,2
T1.64		10,3	-0,1	-10,1
T1.67		6,7	1,6	-5,0
T1.68		-29,4	-28,9	-0,5

membrane deflection values for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa before and after long-term storage during 3.0 years.

Samples/Parameters	Deflection $\Delta P_{def, 1}$, Pa			
	No	Before storage	After storage	Change of modulo values
T5.5		10,3	8,9	-1,4
T5.11		-16,7	3,0	-13,7
T5.17		-8,8	-6,8	-2,0
T5.18		5,7	2,6	-3,1
T5.19		-462,3	3,4	-458,8
T5.20		475,3	8,2	-467,0
T5.24		-23,8	2,6	-21,2
T5.32		-8,5	0,7	-7,8
T5.81		18,0	5,6	-12,4
T5.82		11,0	10,1	-0,9
T5.86		18,0	17,8	-0,3
T5.90		26,1	1,2	-24,9
T5.93		11,0	2,9	-8,1
T5.95		8,1	2,7	-5,4

anical characteristics of pressure sensor chips PDA-NFL for ranges of 1 kPa and 5 kPa before and after long-term storage is summarized in Table 7. Table 7 additionally presents information about:

- sensitivity when pressure is applied from the top side of chip;
- mechanical hysteresis and repeatability;
- noise of output signal;
- burst pressure for membrane;
- change of zero output signal after flipping chip in gravity field.

450
451**Table 7:** Common mechanical characteristics of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa and 5 kPa before and after long-term storage.

Parameters/Range	Pressure side	1 kPa		5 kPa	
Number of samples		8		14	
Using of SO		-		+	
Measurement in relation to storage time		Before	After 4.5 years	Before	After 3.0 years
Zero output signal U_0 , mV		< 100		< 40	
Sensitivity S , mV/V/kPa	Back	41.0 ± 5.5	40.6 ± 6.3	11.4 ± 1.9	11.2 ± 1.8
	Top	39.7 ± 5.6	40.0 ± 6.5	11.3 ± 1.9	11.2 ± 1.8
Nonlinearity $2K_{NL}$, %/FS	Back	1.28 ± 0.36	0.81 ± 0.15	0.11 ± 0.09	0.10 ± 0.06
	Top	1.97 ± 0.62	1.23 ± 0.22	0.18 ± 0.09	0.10 ± 0.06
Zero output stability $dU_{0\text{stab}}$, %/FS	Back	-	1.3 ± 0.8	-	0.9 ± 0.7
Sensitivity stability $dU_{1\text{ or }5\text{stab}}$, %/FS	Back	-	3.5 ± 1.3	-	1.7 ± 0.6
Mechanical hysteresis H , %/FS	Back	0.07 ± 0.07		0.03 ± 0.02	
Mechanical repeatability R , %/FS	Back	0.09 ± 0.06		0.08 ± 0.02	
Noise of output signal ΔU_{noise} , $\mu\text{V/V}$		< 12		< 3	
Burst pressure of membrane P_{burst} , kPa				> 400	
Change of zero output signal after flipping chip in gravity field, μV		72 ± 26		94 ± 47	

452

3.2. Temperature characteristics

453
454
455
456
457
458
459
460
461
462
463
464
465
466
467
468
469

Research of temperature characteristics for two batches of pressure sensors chip PDA-NFL were carried out for two temperature ranges: from -30 °C to +20 °C and from +20 °C to +60 °C. The rate of temperature change in a thermal chamber is 1 °C/min. The holding time of limit temperature values is 1 hour. The studies were carried out in 64 dm³ volume chamber, where we have additional error by the volume temperature gradient and temperature hysteresis at +20 °C after temperature change to -30 °C or +60 °C. A precision temperature control was performed using a group of small-sized temperature sensors based on Schottky diode with planar arrangement of electrodes (PSD chip). The development of PSD chip was previously presented in research [96]. The temperature gradient across the chamber less than 0.9 °C. Considering that all samples remained position during the test period, the same unbalance within the volume can be neglected. The temperature hysteresis of the chamber less than 0.08 °C. It is equivalent errors about 0.0094 %/FS and 0.0013 %/FS for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa and 5 kPa, respectively. It is also negligible error for both type of pressure sensor. Temperature hysteresis and temperature coefficient for zero output signal and sensitivity were considered as parameters for temperature characteristics by the following equations:

$$THZ = \frac{U_0(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}}) - U'_0(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})}{|\Delta U_{1\text{ or }5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})|} \cdot 100\%, \quad (7)$$

$$THS = \frac{\Delta U_{1\text{ or }5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}}) - \Delta U'_{1\text{ or }5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})}{|\Delta U_{1\text{ or }5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})|} \cdot 100\%, \quad (8)$$

$$TCZ = \frac{U_0(T_{-30^\circ\text{C}/+60^\circ\text{C}}) - U_0(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})}{\frac{T_{-30^\circ\text{C}/+60^\circ\text{C}} - T_{+20^\circ\text{C}}}{10} |\Delta U_{1\text{ or }5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})|} \cdot 100\%, \quad (9)$$

$$TCS = \frac{\Delta U_{1\text{ or }5}(T_{-30^\circ\text{C}/+60^\circ\text{C}}) - \Delta U_{1\text{ or }5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})}{\frac{T_{-30^\circ\text{C}/+60^\circ\text{C}} - T_{+20^\circ\text{C}}}{10} |\Delta U_{1\text{ or }5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})|} \cdot 100\%, \quad (10)$$

470
471

where $U_0(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})$ – zero output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 0$ kPa and temperature $T = +20$ °C before the temperature change in chamber, mV; $U'_0(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})$ – zero

output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 0$ kPa and temperature $T = +20$ °C after the temperature change in chamber, mV; $\Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})$ – change of output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 1$ kPa or $\Delta P = 5$ kPa and temperature $T = +20$ °C before the temperature change in chamber, mV; $\Delta U'_{1 \text{ or } 5}(T_{+20^\circ\text{C}})$ – change of output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 1$ kPa or $\Delta P = 5$ kPa and temperature $T = +20$ °C after temperature change in chamber, mV; $U_0(T_{-30^\circ\text{C}/+60^\circ\text{C}})$ – zero output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 0$ kPa and temperature $T = -30$ °C or $T = +60$ °C, mV; $\Delta U_{1 \text{ or } 5}(T_{-30^\circ\text{C}/+60^\circ\text{C}})$ – change of output signal under the influence of pressure $\Delta P = 1$ kPa or $\Delta P = 5$ kPa and temperature $T = -30$ °C or $T = +60$ °C, mV. Pressure was applied only from the back side of chip PDA-NFL. All presented values of temperature characteristics are not significantly different due to the difference in number of samples. The parameters of temperature characteristics before long-term storage have the same range relative to the arithmetic mean values with a scatter from researches [48] and [56]. Table 8 presents all 4 parameters of temperature characteristics for two batches of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL, two temperature ranges, and two moments before and after long-term storage.

Table 8: Temperature characteristics of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 1 kPa and 5 kPa before and after long-term storage.

Parameters/Range	Temperature range	1 kPa		5 kPa	
		8		14	
	Number of samples				
	Measurement in relation to storage time	Before	After 4.5 years	Before	After 3.0 years
Temperature hysteresis of zero	-30...+20 °C	0.36 ± 0.20	0.30 ± 0.28	0.05 ± 0.03	0.03 ± 0.02
output signal THZ, %/FS	+20...+60 °C	0.39 ± 0.38	0.38 ± 0.43	0.07 ± 0.04	0.05 ± 0.02
Temperature hysteresis of sensitivity THS, %/FS	-30...+20 °C	0.63 ± 0.17	0.57 ± 0.18	0.20 ± 0.05	0.07 ± 0.05
	+20...+60 °C	0.39 ± 0.22	0.20 ± 0.18	0.07 ± 0.02	0.05 ± 0.05
Temperature coefficient of zero	-30...+20 °C	0.91 ± 0.56	0.96 ± 0.65	0.12 ± 0.09	0.12 ± 0.07
output signal TCZ, %/10 °C/FS	+20...+60 °C	1.37 ± 0.56	1.36 ± 0.74	0.15 ± 0.09	0.18 ± 0.09
Temperature coefficient of sensitivity TCS, %/10 °C/FS	-30...+20 °C	5.94 ± 1.51	6.34 ± 1.38	2.02 ± 0.11	2.29 ± 0.20
	+20...+60 °C	6.64 ± 0.60	5.94 ± 0.50	2.16 ± 0.54	2.07 ± 0.55

The errors by temperature characteristics have a rather high spread between samples in a batch. If we evaluate the variation of parameters by their arithmetic mean values in two kinds of batches, it can be noted that:

- THZ and THS for two temperature ranges are reduced with different percentage values;
- TCZ remains effectively the same;
- TCS in negative temperature range increases, but TCS in positive temperature range decreases.

The errors by temperature characteristics of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa are significantly lower than analogs for range of 1 kPa. It indicates that a more correct balance for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa has been achieved between the absolute change of useful output signal from temperature (numerator of equations (7-10)) and the sensitivity from pressure in selected ranges (denominator of equations (7-10)). The balance of parameters is a consequence of:

- more qualitatively realized chain of the technological route for creation of chip face with less numbers of defect, effect of which, for example, can be seen in the significant reduction of noise for zero output signal from 12 to 3 $\mu\text{V/V}$;

506 • more temperature-stable membrane design, where the length of RI edges has
507 almost three times longer and thinned part of membrane has the presence of SO. This
508 feature is also the reason for achieving significantly lower nonlinearity for the wider
509 pressure range up to 5 kPa, but, on the other hand, this geometry of RIs would not allow
510 achieving the high sensitivity for range of 1 kPa with the same area of thinned part.

511 4. Conclusions

512 The measurement of all mechanical and temperature characteristics on batches of
513 highly sensitive pressure sensors chip utilizing the new electrical circuit PDA-NFL was
514 carried out after long-term storage. The measurement of parameters was presented after
515 4.5 years of storage for the range of differential pressure up to 1 kPa for 8 samples and
516 after 3.0 years of storage for the range of differential pressure up to 5 kPa for 14 samples.
517 We analyzed the change of useful output signal and errors, which were obtained actually
518 immediately after fabrication, as well as after long-term storage in normal climatic con-
519 ditions. If we consider all output characteristics of reduced number of samples in batches
520 for two pressure ranges up to the moment of storage, then all its parameters in repre-
521 sentation as arithmetic mean values with standard deviation by batches are almost com-
522 pletely within the range of similar values specified in the initial studies of the same
523 samples of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL [48,56]. Individual parameters such as zero
524 output signal, sensitivity, stability of zero output signal and sensitivity, and initial
525 membrane deflection were considered for each sample separately.

526 The main conclusions on the change of mechanical and temperature characteristics
527 of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL after long-term storage are following:

528 • The stability error by absolute values of zero output signal is varied within
529 2.3% for all types of samples. The reason could be a combination of changes in electrical
530 properties of individual 8 passive and 2 active circuit elements with the RMS reduction;

531 • 14 of 14 samples for range of 5 kPa and 5 of 8 samples for range of 1 kPa have
532 decreased sensitivity, which probably indicates the powerful influence of RMS relaxa-
533 tion in used assembly design of pressure sensor. The change of sensitivity for the batch
534 of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL with lower pressure range after 4.5 years of storage
535 ($dU_{1\text{stab}} = (3.5 \pm 1.3) \%/FS$) is nearly 2 times more than value the batch for larger pressure
536 range after 3.0 years of storage ($dU_{5\text{stab}} = (1.7 \pm 0.6) \%/FS$);

537 • Also, the powerful influence of RMS relaxation in used assembly design is
538 evidenced by the unidirectional strict reduction of the initial membrane deflection. The
539 tendency of the assembly design to the balanced unstressed state is observed regardless
540 of whether the structure was initially bent upward or concave downward by RMS ef-
541 fects.

542 • The analysis of nonlinearity variation shows the uniform trend for simulta-
543 neous reduction of errors and convergences of different errors with each other when
544 pressure is applied from different sides of chip. Especially, this effect was demonstrated
545 for the batch of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for range of 5 kPa, where the nonlinearity
546 by applying pressure from both sides has the same values. The balance of nonlinearity,
547 as well as the reduction of the sensitivity difference when applying pressure from dif-
548 ferent sides of chip is the consequence of RMS reduction of stressed initial assembly
549 states;

550 • The reduction of THZ and THS while TCS has the same values is another
551 factor of the significant influence by RMS relaxation. We probably could see the multi-
552 directional change of all temperature characteristics if the effect was more powerful
553 connected with the stability of parameters for each element of PDA-NFL electrical cir-
554 cuit.

555 Each pressure sensor design has its own balance between advantages and disad-
556 vantages as it was mentioned earlier in Introduction. In the case of changing the classical

Wheatstone bridge to PDA-NFL circuit, the advantage of pressure sensor chip is high sensitivity (when pressure is applied from the back side of chip: $S_{1 \text{ after}} = (40.6 \pm 6.4)$ mV/V/kPa for range of 1 kPa and $S_{5 \text{ after}} = (11.2 \pm 1.8)$ mV/V/kPa for range of 5 kPa), which can be achieved on relatively small chip dimensions (4.00x4.00 mm²) and with low mechanical errors: nonlinearity (when pressure is applied from the back side of chip: $2K_{NL \ 1 \text{ after}} = (0.81 \pm 0.15)$ %/FS for range of 1 kPa and $2K_{NL \ 5 \text{ after}} = (0.10 \pm 0.06)$ %/FS for range of 5 kPa), as well as mechanical hysteresis and repeatability. The significantly lower temperature errors for branch of pressure sensor chip for range of 5 kPa are achieved relative to similar branch for range of 1 kPa.

In the present, the significant disadvantage of this development is the choice of the assembly design for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL specifically for low and ultra-low pressure ranges. The errors of pressure sensor chip for low and ultra-low pressure ranges is traditionally higher than for analogs for medium and high pressure ranges. The influence of RMS is significant for a thin membrane with a rather large area. The disadvantage of used assembly design was the reason for the initial increased errors for nonlinearity, when pressure is applied from the different side of chip, and for the temperature hysteresis, which were partially reduced after several years of storage. A solution to this disadvantage would be to modernize the geometry of elements for assembly and the ways of its connection from the sensor case to chip PDA-NFL. The proposed solution is the most actual now, but it can be refuted for pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL, because, for example, the stability of zero output signal is a component from the change of characteristics for each element of PDA-NFL circuit and the whole system of surface construction by planar technology.

Finally, the research of pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL demonstrated the quality of stability of output parameters and explained the reasons and methods to solve it. The research proved the relevance of using pressure sensor chip PDA-NFL for low ranges of 1 and 5 kPa, because for at least 3 years this development maintains extremely high sensitivity values with optimal values of errors in mechanical and temperature characteristics within the required conditions for this application, and, additionally, we have gained knowledge and shown how to improve existing disadvantages.

5. Patents

There are patents resulting from the work reported in this manuscript: RU 195160 U1, RU 195159 U1, RU 187746 U1, RU 187760 U1, RU 174159 U1.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Data associated with the research are available and can be obtained by contacting the author.

Acknowledgments: The studies were financially supported by Dukhov Automatics Research Institute.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

References

1. I-Micronews: MEMS Pressure Sensors – Technologies and Market Trends 2021 Available online: <https://www.i-micronews.com/products/mems-pressure-sensors-technology-and-market-trends-2021>.
2. Mordor Intelligence: MEMS Pressure Sensors Market Size & Share Analysis - Growth Trends & Forecasts (2023 - 2028) Available online: <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/mems-pressure-sensors-market>.
3. Tamaki I.; Tetsu O.; Masaaki N.; Etsutaro K.; Tetsuro T.; Ryuzou A. New DPharp Series Pressure and Differential Pressure Transmitters. *Yokogawa Technical Report English Edition* **2004**, 9–14.

- 604 4. Hamid, Y.; Hutt, D.A.; Whalley, D.C.; Craddock, R. Relative Contributions of Packaging Elements to the Thermal Hysteresis
605 of a MEMS Pressure Sensor. *Sensors* **2020**, *20*, 1727, doi:10.3390/s20061727.
- 606 5. Liu, S.; Du, X.H.; Zhu, M.J.; Liu, D. Long-Term Stability Enabling Technology of Silicon-Based Piezoresistive MEMS
607 Pressure Sensor. *J Phys Conf Ser* **2020**, *1520*, 012009, doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1520/1/012009.
- 608 6. Li, Y.; Liang, T.; Lei, C.; Li, Q.; Li, Z.; Ghaffar, A.; Xiong, J. Study on the Stability of the Electrical Connection of
609 High-Temperature Pressure Sensor Based on the Piezoresistive Effect of P-Type SiC. *Micromachines (Basel)* **2021**, *12*, 216,
610 doi:10.3390/mi12020216.
- 611 7. Zarnik, M.S.; Belavic, D.; Macek, S. The Warm-up and Offset Stability of a Low-Pressure Piezoresistive Ceramic Pressure
612 Sensor. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2010**, *158*, 198–206, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2009.12.035.
- 613 8. Je, C.H.; Lee, S.Q.; Yang, W.S. High Sensitivity Surface Micromachined Absolute Pressure Sensor. *Procedia Eng* **2016**, *168*,
614 725–728, doi:10.1016/j.proeng.2016.11.261.
- 615 9. Futane, N.P.; RoyChowdhury, S.; RoyChaudhuri, C.; Saha, H. Analog ASIC for Improved Temperature Drift Compensation
616 of a High Sensitive Porous Silicon Pressure Sensor. *Analog Integr Circuits Signal Process* **2011**, *67*, 383–393,
617 doi:10.1007/s10470-010-9580-7.
- 618 10. Ginggen, A.; Tardy, Y.; Crivelli, R.; Bork, T.; Renaud, P. A Telemetric Pressure Sensor System for Biomedical Applications.
619 *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng* **2008**, *55*, 1374–1381, doi:10.1109/TBME.2007.913908.
- 620 11. Prigodskiy, D.M.; Basov, M.V. Research of Pressure Sensitive Elements with Increased Strength. *Nano- i Mikrosistemnaya*
621 *Tehnika* **2019**, *21*, 368–376, doi:10.17587/nmst.21.368-376.
- 622 12. Kinnell, P.K.; King, J.; Lester, M.; Craddock, R. A Hollow Stiffening Structure for Low-Pressure Sensors. *Sens Actuators A*
623 *Phys* **2010**, *160*, 35–41, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2010.03.024.
- 624 13. Li, L.; Belov, N.; Klitzke, M.; Park, J.-S. High Performance Piezoresistive Low Pressure Sensors. In Proceedings of the 2016
625 IEEE SENSORS; IEEE, October 2016; pp. 1–3.
- 626 14. Basov, M.; Prigodskiy, D.M. Investigation of High-Sensitivity Piezoresistive Pressure Sensors at Ultra-Low Differential
627 Pressures. *IEEE Sens J* **2020**, *20*, 7646–7652, doi:10.1109/JSEN.2020.2980326.
- 628 15. Wang, J.; Xia, X.; Li, X. Monolithic Integration of Pressure Plus Acceleration Composite TPMS Sensors With a Single-Sided
629 Micromachining Technology. *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems* **2012**, *21*, 284–293, doi:10.1109/JMEMS.2011.2178117.
- 630 16. Basov, M.; Prigodskiy, D. Development of High-Sensitivity Piezoresistive Pressure Sensors for $-0.5...+0.5$ KPa. *Journal of*
631 *Micromechanics and Microengineering* **2020**, *30*, 105006, doi:10.1088/1361-6439/ab9581.
- 632 17. Zhao, L.; Xu, T.; Hebibul, R.; Jiang, Z.; Ding, J.; Peng, N.; Guo, X.; Xu, Y.; Wang, H.; Zhao, Y. A Bossed Diaphragm
633 Piezoresistive Pressure Sensor with a Peninsula–Island Structure for the Ultra-Low-Pressure Range with High Sensitivity.
634 *Meas Sci Technol* **2016**, *27*, 124012, doi:10.1088/0957-0233/27/12/124012.
- 635 18. Kubba, A.E.; Hasson, A.; Kubba, A.I.; Hall, G. A Micro-Capacitive Pressure Sensor Design and Modelling. *Journal of Sensors*
636 *and Sensor Systems* **2016**, *5*, 95–112, doi:10.5194/jsss-5-95-2016.
- 637 19. Belavic, D.; Zarnik, M.S.; Macek, S.; Jerlah, M.; Hrovat, M.; Pavlin, M. Capacitive Pressure Sensors Realized with LTCC
638 Technology. In Proceedings of the 2008 31st International Spring Seminar on Electronics Technology; IEEE, May 2008; pp.
639 269–272.
- 640 20. Xu, M.; Feng, Y.; Han, X.; Ke, X.; Li, G.; Zeng, Y.; Yan, H.; Li, D. Design and Fabrication of an Absolute Pressure MEMS
641 Capacitance Vacuum Sensor Based on Silicon Bonding Technology. *Vacuum* **2021**, *186*, 110065,
642 doi:10.1016/j.vacuum.2021.110065.
- 643 21. Xu, M.; Han, X.; Zhao, C.; Li, G.; Zeng, Y.; Li, D.; Yan, H.; Feng, Y. Design and Fabrication of a MEMS Capacitance Vacuum
644 Sensor Based on Silicon Buffer Block. *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems* **2020**, *29*, 1556–1562,
645 doi:10.1109/JMEMS.2020.3032573.

- 646 22. Ghanam, M.; Goldschmidtboeing, F.; Bilger, T.; Bucherer, A.; Woias, P. MEMS Shielded Capacitive Pressure and Force
647 Sensors with Excellent Thermal Stability and High Operating Temperature. *Sensors* **2023**, *23*, 4248, doi:10.3390/s23094248.
- 648 23. Pernu, T.; Saari-Lahti, J.; Kyynarainen, J.; Sillanpaa, T. Ultra-High Sensitivity Surface-Micromachined Capacitive Differential
649 Pressure Sensor for Low-Pressure Applications. *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems* **2023**, *32*, 74–81,
650 doi:10.1109/JMEMS.2022.3218857.
- 651 24. Murakami, Y.; Shingyouji, T. Separation and Analysis of Diffusion and Generation Components of Pn Junction Leakage
652 Current in Various Silicon Wafers. *J Appl Phys* **1994**, *75*, 3548–3552, doi:10.1063/1.356091.
- 653 25. Sager, K.; Gerlach, G.; Nakladal, A.; Schroth, A. Ambient Humidity and Moisture — a Decisive Failure Source in
654 Piezoresistive Sensors. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **1995**, *46*, 171–175, doi:10.1016/0924-4247(94)00884-K.
- 655 26. *Handbook of Silicon Based MEMS Materials and Technologies*; Lindroos V., Tilli M., Lehto A., Motooka T., Eds.; Elsevier: Oxford,
656 2010; ISBN 9780815515944.
- 657 27. *Fundamentals of Industrial Electronics*; Wilamowski, B.M., Irwin, J.D., Eds.; CRC Press, 2018; ISBN 9781315218441.
- 658 28. Martin, B.; Rathi, A.; Kliem, H. Surface Charging of Silicodioxide/Silicon Structures. *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and*
659 *Electrical Insulation* **2012**, *19*, 1124–1131, doi:10.1109/TDEI.2012.6259979.
- 660 29. Bentarzi, H.; Zitouni, A.; Kribes, Y. Oxide Charges Densities Determination Using Charge-Pumping Technique With BTS in
661 MOS Structures. *WSEAS TRANSACTIONS on ELECTRONICS* **2008**, *5*, 101–110.
- 662 30. Liu, Y.; Wang, H.; Zhao, W.; Qin, H.; Fang, X. Thermal-Performance Instability in Piezoresistive Sensors: Inducement and
663 Improvement. *Sensors* **2016**, *16*, 1984, doi:10.3390/s16121984.
- 664 31. Chiou, J.A.; Chen, S. Thermal Hysteresis Analysis of MEMS Pressure Sensors. *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems* **2005**,
665 *14*, 782–787, doi:10.1109/JMEMS.2005.845460.
- 666 32. Andrei, A.; Malhaire, C.; Brida, S.; Barbier, D. Long-Term Stability of Metal Lines, Polysilicon Gauges, and Ohmic Contacts
667 for Harsh-Environment Pressure Sensors. *IEEE Sens J* **2006**, *6*, 1596–1601, doi:10.1109/JSEN.2006.884164.
- 668 33. Sandvand, A.; Halvorsen, E.; Aasmundtveit, K.E.; Jakobsen, H. Identification and Elimination of Hygro-Thermo-
669 Mechanical Stress-Effects in a High-Precision MEMS Pressure Sensor. *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems* **2017**, *26*,
670 415–423, doi:10.1109/JMEMS.2017.2651162.
- 671 34. Birkelund, K.; Gravesen, P.; Shiryaev, S.; Rasmussen, P.B.; Rasmussen, M.D. High-Pressure Silicon Sensor with Low-Cost
672 Packaging. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2001**, *92*, 16–22, doi:10.1016/S0924-4247(01)00534-9.
- 673 35. Zarnik, M.S.; Rocak, D.; Macek, S. Residual Stresses in a Pressure-Sensor Package Induced by Adhesive Material during
674 Curing: A Case Study. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2004**, *116*, 442–449, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2004.05.010.
- 675 36. Suzuki, Y.; Kudo, T.; Ikeda, K. Accurate, Cost Effective Absolute Pressure Sensor. In Proceedings of the Proceedings of
676 International Solid State Sensors and Actuators Conference (Transducers '97); IEEE; pp. 1493–1496.
- 677 37. Xu, Z.; Yan, J.; Ji, M.; Zhou, Y.; Wang, D.; Wang, Y.; Mai, Z.; Zhao, X.; Nan, T.; Xing, G.; et al. An SOI-Structured
678 Piezoresistive Differential Pressure Sensor with High Performance. *Micromachines (Basel)* **2022**, *13*, 2250,
679 doi:10.3390/mi13122250.
- 680 38. Meena, K. V.; Sankar, A.R. Biomedical Catheters With Integrated Miniature Piezoresistive Pressure Sensors: A Review. *IEEE*
681 *Sens J* **2021**, *21*, 10241–10290, doi:10.1109/JSEN.2021.3057222.
- 682 39. Liu, Y.; Jiang, X.; Yang, H.; Qin, H.; Wang, W. Structural Engineering in Piezoresistive Micropressure Sensors: A Focused
683 Review. *Micromachines (Basel)* **2023**, *14*, 1507, doi:10.3390/mi14081507.
- 684 40. Fiorillo, A.S.; Critello, C.D.; Pullano, S.A. Theory, Technology and Applications of Piezoresistive Sensors: A Review. *Sens*
685 *Actuators A Phys* **2018**, *281*, 156–175, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2018.07.006.
- 686 41. He, F.; Feng, Y.; Dai, J.; Li, J. Design for Silicon Piezoresistive Pressure Sensor Chips. *IEEE Trans Compon Packaging Manuf*
687 *Technol* **2023**, *13*, 920–927, doi:10.1109/TCPMT.2023.3295799.

- 688 42. Doll, J.C.; Pruitt, B.L. *Piezoresistor Design and Applications*; Springer New York: New York, NY, 2013; ISBN 978-1-4614-8516-2.
- 689 43. Basov, M. Development of High-Sensitivity Pressure Sensor with on-Chip Differential Transistor Amplifier. *Journal of*
690 *Micromechanics and Microengineering* **2020**, *30*, 065001, doi:10.1088/1361-6439/ab82f1.
- 691 44. Basov, M. High-Sensitivity MEMS Pressure Sensor Utilizing Bipolar Junction Transistor with Temperature Compensation.
692 *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2020**, *303*, 111705, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2019.111705.
- 693 45. Basov, M.V.; Prigodskiy, D.M. Investigation of a Sensitive Element for the Pressure Sensor Based on a Bipolar
694 Piezotransistor. *Nano- i Mikrosistemnaya Tehnika* **2017**, *19*, 685–693, doi:10.17587/nmst.19.685-693.
- 695 46. Basov, M.; Prigodskiy, D.; Kholodkov, D. Modeling of Sensitive Element for Pressure Sensor Based on Bipolar
696 Piezotransistor. *Sensors and Systems* **2017**, *6*, 17–24.
- 697 47. Basov, M. Pressure Sensor with Novel Electrical Circuit Utilizing Bipolar Junction Transistor. In Proceedings of the 2021
698 IEEE Sensors; IEEE, October 31 2021; pp. 1–4.
- 699 48. Basov, M. High Sensitive, Linear and Thermostable Pressure Sensor Utilizing Bipolar Junction Transistor for 5 KPa. *Phys Scr*
700 **2021**, *96*, 065705, doi:10.1088/1402-4896/abf536.
- 701 49. Tran, A.V.; Zhang, X.; Zhu, B. The Development of a New Piezoresistive Pressure Sensor for Low Pressures. *IEEE*
702 *Transactions on Industrial Electronics* **2018**, *65*, 6487–6496, doi:10.1109/TIE.2017.2784341.
- 703 50. Li, C.; Cordovilla, F.; Jagdheesh, R.; Ocaña, J.L. Design and Optimization of a Novel Structural MEMS Piezoresistive
704 Pressure Sensor. *Microsystem Technologies* **2017**, *23*, 4531–4541, doi:10.1007/s00542-016-3187-6.
- 705 51. Li, C.; Cordovilla, F.; Jagdheesh, R.; Ocaña, J. Design Optimization and Fabrication of a Novel Structural SOI Piezoresistive
706 Pressure Sensor with High Accuracy. *Sensors* **2018**, *18*, 439, doi:10.3390/s18020439.
- 707 52. Huang, X.; Zhang, D. Structured Diaphragm with a Centre Boss and Four Peninsulas for High Sensitivity and High
708 Linearity Pressure Sensors. *Micro Nano Lett* **2014**, *9*, 460–463, doi:10.1049/mnl.2014.0154.
- 709 53. Tran, A.; Zhang, X.; Zhu, B. Mechanical Structural Design of a Piezoresistive Pressure Sensor for Low-Pressure
710 Measurement: A Computational Analysis by Increases in the Sensor Sensitivity. *Sensors* **2018**, *18*, 2023,
711 doi:10.3390/s18072023.
- 712 54. Huang, X.; Zhang, D. High Sensitive and Linear Pressure Sensor for Ultra-Low Pressure Measurement. *Procedia Eng* **2014**, *87*,
713 1202–1205, doi:10.1016/j.proeng.2014.11.383.
- 714 55. Tian, B.; Zhao, Y.; Jiang, Z.; Hu, B. The Design and Analysis of Beam-Membrane Structure Sensors for Micro-Pressure
715 Measurement. *Review of Scientific Instruments* **2012**, *83*, doi:10.1063/1.3702809.
- 716 56. Basov, M. Ultra-High Sensitivity MEMS Pressure Sensor Utilizing Bipolar Junction Transistor for Pressures Ranging From
717 –1 to 1 KPa. *IEEE Sens J* **2021**, *21*, 4357–4364, doi:10.1109/JSEN.2020.3033813.
- 718 57. Xu, T.; Lu, D.; Zhao, L.; Jiang, Z.; Wang, H.; Guo, X.; Li, Z.; Zhou, X.; Zhao, Y. Application and Optimization of Stiffness
719 Abruption Structures for Pressure Sensors with High Sensitivity and Anti-Overload Ability. *Sensors* **2017**, *17*, 1965,
720 doi:10.3390/s17091965.
- 721 58. Yu, Z.; Zhao, Y.; Li, L.; Li, C.; Liu, Y.; Tian, B. Realization of a Micro Pressure Sensor with High Sensitivity and Overload by
722 Introducing Beams and Islands. *Microsystem Technologies* **2015**, *21*, 739–747, doi:10.1007/s00542-014-2234-4.
- 723 59. *The Piezojunction Effect in Silicon Integrated Circuits and Sensors*; Kluwer Academic Publishers: Boston, 2003; Vol. 682; ISBN
724 1-4020-7053-5.
- 725 60. Creemer, J.F.; Fruett, F.; Meijer, G.C.M.; French, P.J. The Piezojunction Effect in Silicon Sensors and Circuits and Its Relation
726 to Piezoresistance. *IEEE Sens J* **2001**, *1*, 98, doi:10.1109/JSEN.2001.936927.
- 727 61. Barlian, A.A.; Park, W.-T.; Mallon, J.R.; Rastegar, A.J.; Pruitt, B.L. Review: Semiconductor Piezoresistance for Microsystems.
728 *Proceedings of the IEEE* **2009**, *97*, 513–552, doi:10.1109/JPROC.2009.2013612.

- 729 62. Babichev, G.G.; Kozlovskiy, S.I.; Romanov, V.A.; Sharan, N.N. Silicon Pressure Transducers with Frequency Output on Base
730 Strain Sensitive Unijunction Transistors. In Proceedings of the Proceedings of IEEE Sensors; IEEE; pp. 998–1001.
- 731 63. Zhang, Z.-H.; Yan-Hong Zhang; Liu, L.-T.; Tian-Ling Ren A Novel MEMS Pressure Sensor with MOSFET on Chip. In
732 Proceedings of the 2008 IEEE Sensors; IEEE, October 2008; pp. 1564–1567.
- 733 64. Futane, N.P.; Chowdhury, S.R.; Chowdhury, C.R.; Saha, H. ANN Based CMOS ASIC Design for Improved
734 Temperature-Drift Compensation of Piezoresistive Micro-Machined High Resolution Pressure Sensor. *Microelectronics
735 Reliability* **2010**, *50*, 282–291, doi:10.1016/j.microrel.2009.09.012.
- 736 65. Dalola, S.; Ferrari, V.; Marioli, D. A MEMS Piezoresistive Inclination Sensor with CMOS ASIC Front-End Interface. In; 2010;
737 pp. 353–357.
- 738 66. Gao, X.; Mackowiak, P.; Mukhopadhyay, B.; Ehrmann, O.; Lang, K.D.; Ngo, H.D. Evaluation and Signal Conditioning of
739 Piezoresistive Silicon Pressure Sensor. *Applied Mechanics and Materials* **2014**, *530–531*, 28–32,
740 doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMM.530-531.28.
- 741 67. Kanda, Y. A Graphical Representation of the Piezoresistance Coefficients in Silicon. *IEEE Trans Electron Devices* **1982**, *29*,
742 64–70, doi:10.1109/T-ED.1982.20659.
- 743 68. Han, J.; Yin, Y.J.; Han, D.; Dong, L. Improved PECVD Si_xN_y Film as a Mask Layer for Deep Wet Etching of the Silicon. *Mater
744 Res Express* **2017**, *4*, 096301, doi:10.1088/2053-1591/aa8782.
- 745 69. Pal, P.; Swarnalatha, V.; Rao, A.V.N.; Pandey, A.K.; Tanaka, H.; Sato, K. High Speed Silicon Wet Anisotropic Etching for
746 Applications in Bulk Micromachining: A Review. *Micro and Nano Systems Letters* **2021**, *9*, 4, doi:10.1186/s40486-021-00129-0.
- 747 70. Canavese, G.; Marasso, S.L.; Quaglio, M.; Cocuzza, M.; Ricciardi, C.; Pirri, C.F. Polymeric Mask Protection for Alternative
748 KOH Silicon Wet Etching. *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering* **2007**, *17*, 1387–1393, doi:10.1088/0960-1317/17/7/022.
- 749 71. Dalvi-Malhotra, J.; Zhong, X.F.; Planje, C.; Brand, G.; Yess, K. A Spin-on Photosensitive Polymeric Etch Protection Mask for
750 Anisotropic Wet Etching of Silicon. *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering* **2008**, *18*, 025029,
751 doi:10.1088/0960-1317/18/2/025029.
- 752 72. Johnson, R.H.; Karbassi, S.; Sridhar, U.; Speldrich, B. A High-Sensitivity Ribbed and Bossed Pressure Transducer. *Sens
753 Actuators A Phys* **1992**, *35*, 93–99, doi:10.1016/0924-4247(92)80146-T.
- 754 73. Huang, X.; Zhang, D. A High Sensitivity and High Linearity Pressure Sensor Based on a Peninsula-Structured Diaphragm
755 for Low-Pressure Ranges. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2014**, *216*, 176–189, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2014.05.031.
- 756 74. Mallon, J.R.; Pourahmadi, F.; Petersen, K.; Barth, P.; Vermeulen, T.; Bryzek, J. Low-Pressure Sensors Employing Bossed
757 Diaphragms and Precision Etch-Stopping. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **1990**, *21*, 89–95, doi:10.1016/0924-4247(90)85018-Y.
- 758 75. Sandmaier, H.; Kuhl, K. A Square-Diaphragm Piezoresistive Pressure Sensor with a Rectangular Central Boss for
759 Low-Pressure Ranges. *IEEE Trans Electron Devices* **1993**, *40*, 1754–1759, doi:10.1109/16.277331.
- 760 76. Berns, A.; Buder, U.; Obermeier, E.; Wolter, A.; Leder, A. AeroMEMS Sensor Array for High-Resolution Wall Pressure
761 Measurements. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2006**, *132*, 104–111, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2006.04.056.
- 762 77. Liu, X.; Yang, Z. An Investigation of Process Variations and Mismatch Characteristics of Vertical Bipolar Junction
763 Transistors. *IEEE Access* **2023**, *11*, 86480–86488, doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3305278.
- 764 78. Kung, F.; Chuah, H.T. A Study on the Stability of Bipolar-Junction-Transistor Formulation in Finite-Difference
765 Time-Domain Framework. *IEEE Trans Microw Theory Tech* **2005**, *53*, 1189–1196, doi:10.1109/TMTT.2005.845744.
- 766 79. Buono, B.; Allerstam, F.; Domeij, M.; Konstantinov, A.; Gumaelius, K.; Das, H.; Neyer, T. Stability of Current Gain in SiC
767 BJTs. *Materials Science Forum* **2014**, *778–780*, 1017–1020, doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/MSF.778-780.1017.
- 768 80. Chou, T.-L.; Chu, C.-H.; Lin, C.-T.; Chiang, K.-N. Sensitivity Analysis of Packaging Effect of Silicon-Based Piezoresistive
769 Pressure Sensor. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2009**, *152*, 29–38, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2009.03.007.

- 770 81. Krondorfer, R.; Kim, Y.K.; Kim, J.; Gustafson, C.-G.; Lommasson, T.C. Finite Element Simulation of Package Stress in
771 Transfer Molded MEMS Pressure Sensors. *Microelectronics Reliability* **2004**, *44*, 1995–2002, doi:10.1016/j.microrel.2004.05.020.
- 772 82. *Handbook of Wafer Bonding*; Ramm, P., Lu, J.J., Taklo, M.M. V., Eds.; Wiley, 2012; ISBN 9783527326464.
- 773 83. Kober, T.; Werthschützky, R. Wafer Level Processing of Overload-Resistant Pressure Sensors. *Procedia Eng* **2012**, *47*, 615–618,
774 doi:10.1016/j.proeng.2012.09.222.
- 775 84. Chang, J.-S.; Lin, J.-Y.; Ho, S.-C.; Lee, Y.-J. Wafer Level Glass Frit Bonding for MEMS Hermetic Packaging. In Proceedings of
776 the 2010 5th International Microsystems Packaging Assembly and Circuits Technology Conference; IEEE, October 2010; pp.
777 1–4.
- 778 85. Knechtel, R.; Zellmer, M.; Schikowski, M.; Behmueller, M.; Van Buggenhout, C.; Petropoulos, A. Glass Frit Wafer Bonding
779 for Encapsulating Monolithic Integrated CMOS-MEMS Devices. *ECS Trans* **2018**, *86*, 111–118, doi:10.1149/08605.0111ecst.
- 780 86. Liu, Q.; Du, L.; Zhao, Z.; Xiao, L.; Sun, X. Localized Si–Au Eutectic Bonding around Sunken Pad for Fabrication of a
781 Capacitive Absolute Pressure Sensor. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2013**, *201*, 241–245, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2013.07.013.
- 782 87. Lee, K.R.; Kim, K.; Park, H.-D.; Kim, Y.K.; Choi, S.-W.; Choi, W.-B. Fabrication of Capacitive Absolute Pressure Sensor Using
783 Si–Au Eutectic Bonding in SOI Wafer. *J Phys Conf Ser* **2006**, *34*, 393–398, doi:10.1088/1742-6596/34/1/064.
- 784 88. Wandowski, T.; Moll, J.; Malinowski, P.; Opoka, S.; Ostachowicz, W. Assessment of Piezoelectric Sensor Adhesive Bonding.
785 *J Phys Conf Ser* **2015**, *628*, 012114, doi:10.1088/1742-6596/628/1/012114.
- 786 89. Pang, C.; Zhao, Z.; Du, L.; Fang, Z. Adhesive Bonding with SU-8 in a Vacuum for Capacitive Pressure Sensors. *Sens Actuators*
787 *A Phys* **2008**, *147*, 672–676, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2008.06.001.
- 788 90. Schumacher, A.; Shah, V.; Steckemetz, S.; Dietrich, G.; Pflug, E.; Hehn, T.; Knappmann, S.; Dehé, A.; Leson, A. Improved
789 Mounting of Strain Sensors by Reactive Bonding. *J Mater Eng Perform* **2021**, *30*, 7796–7804, doi:10.1007/s11665-021-05993-w.
- 790 91. Schwenck, A.; Grözinger, T.; Günther, T.; Schumacher, A.; Schuhmacher, D.; Werum, K.; Zimmermann, A. Characterization
791 of a PCB Based Pressure Sensor and Its Joining Methods for the Metal Membrane. *Sensors* **2021**, *21*, 5557,
792 doi:10.3390/s21165557.
- 793 92. Wang, Q.; Yang, X.; Zhang, Y.; Ding, J. A Simple Thermo-Compression Bonding Setup for Wire Bonding Interconnection in
794 Pressure Sensor Silicon Chip Packaging. *Microsystem Technologies* **2011**, *17*, 1629–1633, doi:10.1007/s00542-011-1345-4.
- 795 93. He, F.; Huang, Q.-A.; Qin, M. A Silicon Directly Bonded Capacitive Absolute Pressure Sensor. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2007**,
796 *135*, 507–514, doi:10.1016/j.sna.2006.09.022.
- 797 94. Kim, S.; Park, J.; So, S.; Ahn, S.; Choi, J.; Koo, C.; Joung, Y.-H. Characteristics of an Implantable Blood Pressure Sensor
798 Packaged by Ultrafast Laser Microwelding. *Sensors* **2019**, *19*, 1801, doi:10.3390/s19081801.
- 799 95. Wang, J.; Li, X. Package-Friendly Piezoresistive Pressure Sensors with on-Chip Integrated Packaging-Stress-Suppressed
800 Suspension (PS³) Technology. *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering* **2013**, *23*, 045027,
801 doi:10.1088/0960-1317/23/4/045027.
- 802 96. Basov, M. Schottky Diode Temperature Sensor for Pressure Sensor. *Sens Actuators A Phys* **2021**, *331*, 112930,
803 doi:10.1016/j.sna.2021.112930.

804

805 **Disclaimer/Publisher's Note:** The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual
806 author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any in-jury
807 to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.

808